

SCAVENGING AND SECURITY CHALLENGES IN AKWA IBOM STATE: A CASE ANALYSIS OF UYO METROPOLIS

Unwana-Abasi S. Udoh

unwanabasi06@gmail.com

08023139391

Department of Public Administration

Akwa Ibom State University

Obio Akpa Campus, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study investigates the reason why scavenging business has degenerate to the extent of becoming security risk by generating several security challenges in the state. The objective of the study was to find out the reasons whether scavengers were responsible for security challenges in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis. The ex-post facto research design, and content analysis were adopted as for the study. The study adopted the Theory of Human Needs by Abraham Maslow as its theoretical framework. The study asked a question to know whether scavengers were responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis. The only finding in the study as drawn from the empirical survey showed that, Scavengers also directly responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis. Based on the finding, it was recommended that, the State Government should strengthen its Task Force on Scavenging and other Criminal Offenses by providing special funding and also conscripting members of the rural communities to watch over the activities of scavengers in their various communities and report any criminal element to law enforcement agency in the state.

KEYWORDS: Scavenging, Security Challenges, Rural Communities and Metropolis.

INTRODUCTION

The term, "scavenging" is severally connoted. Technically, "Scavenging," according to Clerk (2019) is the process of replacing the exhaust gas in a cylinder of an internal combustion engine with the fresh air/fuel mixture (or fresh air, in the case of direct-injection engines) for the next cycle. If scavenging is incomplete, the remaining exhaust gases can cause improper combustion for the next cycle, leading to reduced power output. In animal kingdom, Scavengers are animals that consume dead organisms that have died from causes other than predation or have been killed by other predators. Tan et al (2011) opine that, while scavenging generally refers to carnivores feeding on carrion, it is also a herbivorous feeding behaviour. But, Getz (2011) asserts that scavengers play an important role in the ecosystem by consuming dead animal and plant material. Decomposer and detritivores complete this

process, by consuming the remains left by scavengers.

Scavengers aid in overcoming fluctuations of food resources in the environment (Castilla, et al., 2011). And, according to Turner, et al (2017) the process and rate of scavenging is affected by both biotic and abiotic factors, such as carcass size, habitat, temperature, and seasons. But, whereas, in human environment, scavengers are human beings. That is why the state government could deal with them when their activities began to take anti-social dimension in parts of Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis. The Akwa Ibom State government has banned the activities of scavengers in the state (The Pioneer News Paper, April 5, 2023).

On the other hand, security challenges are yet another phenomenon in the socio-political landscape of Akwa Ibom State. The issue of security has almost, if not totally become a nightmare to the state government, especially since the advent of the scavengers, who are basically from the northern part of the country. It is based on this premise that Udoh et al (2021) have asserted that "the issue of security of lives and property in Nigeria has been in the front burner in recent times and has attracted global attention, mostly in this 21st century. Every now and then, cases of insecurity like: threats, killings, kidnappings, bombings, etc. are heard in parts of the country. Some other security issues manifest themselves in the forms of terrorism, insurgency, banditry, protests, or civil unrest/strife. Lately, Nigerians as well as foreigners, resident in Nigeria have been enmeshed in a firebox of insecurity leading to a score of deaths and destruction of property worth millions of naira in the country." This assertion is corroborated by Udoh et al (2023) who stated that "there are many notable security challenges that have affected Nigeria from time to time. Some of this challenges include; Kidnapping, militancy, (Islamist) in the North East; Biafra (separatist) in the South East; Niger Delta Avengers in the South-South, etc. However, Boko Haram group remains Nigeria's biggest security threat, particularly in the North East. For many years now, it has been observed that insecurity in Nigeria has increased..."

In Akwa Ibom State there is a fast growing population of the northerners comprising the herders, i.e. the cattle rearers; the scavengers; and others. But, in particular, the activities of the scavengers which at the initial stage had the outlook of a legitimate business that could feign for economic prosperity of the operators, suddenly metamorphosed into violent adventure and later began to take anti-social dimension in parts of Akwa Ibom State to the extent that safety was almost eroded, particularly in Uyo metropolis. It would be recalled that in a few years now, there have been a growing population of Northerners, particularly the Hausas and the Fulanis. These people who seem naturally very innocent, but hardworking, on arrival in the state took to all kinds of jobs, both major and or menial jobs like: trading on all sorts of things such as forex, clothing, food stuff, cows, goats, rams, shoe making and or polishing, nail cutting, sowing as well as nomadic agriculture of raising of cows and other animals. Some others, on nomadic nature also took to scavenging of condemn iron, plastics and other saleable materials. While others like the clothe sellers, shoe maker, nail cutters, etc. usually moved from one place to another to scout for their customers, the scavengers moved with wheelbarrows to convey their wares to their various dump sites. At the end of the day, these wares are sold in large scale to truck drivers for further conveyance to the north.

However, when crises began to ensue between the scavengers and the citizens of Akwa Ibom State, the State Government first of all issued a warning to the Northerners to go about their legitimate businesses with decorum in the state. When the situation persisted, the

State Government placed a ban and set a Task Force on the use of wheelbarrows, which were almost becoming a nuisance to motorists and other road users, as they always pushed their barrows in opposite direction and with audacity on the road. When that was done, they resorted to using bags to convey their wares. It was further crisis which claimed the life of a citizen in Afaha Oku in Uyo metropolis as well as the lives and property of other citizen, including the lives and property of some of the Northerners, that the State Government saw that the metropolis was no longer safe, hence the total ban by the state government.

It is against this backdrop that the researcher is compelled to investigate the reason why scavenging business has degenerate to the extent of becoming security risk by generating several security challenges in the state.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

In Nigeria, the Northerners are culturally farmers with a strong bias or flair for nomadic agriculture. But, lately there had been a rapid influx of migrants leading to the growing population of these Northerners, particularly the Hausas and the Fulanis in Akwa Ibom State. In Akwa Ibom State, study shows that among this huge population of the northerners comprises the herders, i.e. the cattle rearers; the scavengers; and others. It should be noted that the focus of this study is on the scavengers, who form the bulk of the above population. Their nuisance value cannot be compared to the mopping up of waste materials from the environment that they work on as their routine. They openly defecate anywhere around the environments, and on the issue of environment Udoh (2024) upholds that "open defecation can pollute the environment and cause health problem and diseases." As a corroboration on the above assertion, Udoh (2022) maintains that, "environmental pollution ranging from... smell from heaps of dumpsites... all have various effects on human health..."

Notably, however, these people who seemed naturally very innocent, but hardworking, on arrival in the state took to all kinds of jobs, both major and menial jobs like: trading on all sorts of things such as forex, clothing, food stuff, cows, goats, rams, shoe making and or polishing, nail cutting, sowing as well as nomadic agriculture of raising of cows and other animals. Some others, on nomadic nature also took to scavenging of condemn iron, plastics and other saleable materials. While others like the clothe sellers, shoe maker, nail cutters, etc. usually moved from one place to another to scout for their customers, the scavengers moved with wheelbarrows to convey their wares to their various dumpsites. At the end of the day, these wares are sold in large scale to truck drivers for further conveyance to the north.

The activities of scavengers which at the initial stage had the outlook of a legitimate business that could feign for economic prosperity of the operators, suddenly metamorphosed into violent adventure and later began to take anti-social dimension in parts of Akwa Ibom State to the extent that safety was almost eroded, particularly in Uyo metropolis. However, when crises began to ensue between the scavengers and the citizens of Akwa Ibom State, the State Government first of all issued a warning to the Northerners to go about their legitimate businesses with decorum in the state. When the situation persisted, the State Government placed a ban and set a Task Force on the use of wheelbarrows, which were almost becoming a nuisance to motorists and other road users, as they always pushed their barrows one way (in the opposite direction) and with audacity on the road. When that was done, they resorted to using bags to convey their wares. It was further crisis which claimed the life of a citizen in

Afaha Oku in Uyo metropolis as well as the lives and property of other citizen, including the lives and property of some of the Northerners, that the State Government saw that the metropolis was no longer safe, hence the total ban by the state government. But, despite the intervention of government, scavenging business is still going on in the state with rebranded strategies, like using bags, instead of wheel barrows to convey their wares and or waiting at their dump sites for citizens to bring the condemn materials to sell for the at exorbitant prices, etc. It is against this backdrop that the researcher is compelled to investigate the reason why scavenging business has degenerate to the extent of becoming security risk by generating several security challenges in the state.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this research is to investigate the reason why scavenging has degenerate to becoming security risk to the state. The following forms the subsidiary objective of the study;

To find out whether scavengers are responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis.

OPERATIONALIZATION OF CONCEPTS

Scavenging: Going by the various perspectives of scavenging in the introduction of this research, one will be confused of what the study is all about and what it is aiming at. But, for the purpose of clarity, scavenging in the context of this study refers to the activity of human beings to search through waste for things that can be used or eaten.

Security Challenges: Security Challenges are those problems, conflicts or issues arising from the activities of scavengers to source for or excavate condemn irons and materials that have some forms of economic value and are saleable for cash. These challenges or conflicts usually arise between the scavengers and the owners of the materials, when the owners do not want the scavengers to go with those materials. Udoh, et al (2023) has observed that "there are many notable security challenges.... Some of these challenges include: kidnapping, militancy... etc."

Rural Communities: Udoh, *et al* (2023) assert that "there are many types of environments in which humans live. The majority of the people in the world and in the United States of America live in urban settings such as cities and suburban neighbor-hoods because of the greater number of resources and opportunities afforded to the people there. A smaller percentage still live in the rural communities around the world. Rural communities lack the characteristics with which Udoh (2017) cited in Udoh (2020) to include social amenities like: electricity, good road network, portable water, healthcare centres, schools, etc. The author further argued that, "no developed or urban centre has attained its present status except that at one point or the other it was a rural community."

Metropolis: A metropolis is a large, important city. It is usually the capital city of a country, region, or state. In their quest to understand the implications of power outages on the value chain, Udoh et al. (2023) have worked on Uyo and Eket metropolis. In the context of this research, Uyo is the metropolis or metropolitan city of Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Willie *et al* (2016) spoke about men scavenging a dead horse during World War II (at the end of the Battle of Berlin), on Manfred-von-Richthofen-Strabe in Tempelhof borough, 1945. In the 1980s, Lewis Binford suggested that early humans primarily obtained meat via scavenging, not hunting. In 2010, Dennis Bramble and Daniel Lieberman proposed that early carnivorous human ancestors subsequently developed long-distance running behaviours which improved the ability to scavenge and hunt: they could reach scavenging sites more quickly and also pursue a single animal until it could be safely killed at close range due to exhaustion and hyperthermia (Henning *et al*, 2010).

According to O'Bryan (2019), in Tibetan Buddhism the practice of excarnation – that is, the exposure of dead human bodies to carrion birds and/or other scavenging animals – is the distinctive characteristic of sky burial, which involves the dismemberment of human cadavers of whom the remains are fed to vultures, and traditionally the main funeral rite (alongside cremation) used to dispose of the human body (Binford, 1985). But, according to Lieberman *et al* (2007), a similar funerary practice that features excarnation can be found in Zoroastrianism; to prevent the pollution of the sacred elements (fire, earth, and water) from contact with decomposing bodies, human cadavers are exposed on the Tower of Silence to be eaten by vultures and wild dogs.

According to Olson *et al* (2016), studies in behavioural and ecological epidemiology have shown that cannibalistic necrophagy, although rare, has been observed as a survival behaviour in several social species, including anatomically modern humans; [a](#) however, episodes of human cannibalism [m](#) occur rarely in most human societies. Many instances have occurred in human history, especially in times of war and famine, where necrophagy and human cannibalism emerged as a survival behaviour, although anthropologists report the usage of ritual cannibalism among funerary practices and as the preferred means of disposal of the dead in some tribal societies (Kapstein, 2014; Huff, 2004 and Conklin, 1995).

There are many types of environments in which humans live. The majority of people in the world and in the United States live in urban settings, such as cities and suburban neighbourhoods, because of the greater number of resources and opportunities afforded to people in cities. A smaller percentage, however, still live in rural communities around the world. What is a rural community? The definition of rural living changes depending on several different variables.

The Pioneer News Paper of April 5, 2023, a pivotal local tabloid in the state, provides a comprehensive engagement of the government of Akwa Ibom State in curbing the security challenges engendered by the activities of the scavengers in the state. "...government has banned the activities of scavengers in the state. Secretary to State Government, Dr. Emmanuel Ekuwem, in a statement on Tuesday, said the ban is due to the acts of criminality and threat to peaceful inter-ethnic relationships posed by the scavengers in the state. He also said the government's action is also in consonance with "public sentiments amidst popular complaints against the activities of these scavengers who wantonly violate peoples' properties, stealing and assaulting law-abiding citizens in the process."

He said, "Recall that sometime in 2021, multiple explosions, causing fatalities, were recorded in Oruk Anam Local Government Area in the course of scavengers sorting out what turned out to be military brand explosives. About four lives were lost in this incident. Similarly, on 2nd January 2022 scavengers violated the premises of a citizen in Afaha Oku,

Uyo Local Government Area in an attempt to cart away properties. While attempting to prevent the scavengers, the citizen was callously murdered in cold blood while mob action was visited on the scavenger assailants causing the death of the two scavengers. Sundays appear to be the busiest day for these scavengers who take advantage of mass Church attendance to invade homes and cart away valuables leaving hapless citizens with tales of woe upon their return from Church. "As a responsible government, we can no longer tolerate the activities of this industry which is in no way adding value to the socio-economic well-being of the state but rather escalating tensions and threatening the overall peace and security of the state. Accordingly, the operations of scrap scavengers in the state are banned forthwith. Violators of this ban will be apprehended and dealt with according to the law."

Ekuwem also expressed the state government's displeasure at the defiance of the ban on the activities of motorcycles within the Uyo metropolis and environs. He said, "Government has observed with dismay and serious concern the flagrant defiance of the ban on motorcycle operations within Uyo metropolis and environs. This ban is hereby reiterated with a warning that defaulters stand to lose not only their motorcycles if apprehended but also risk being prosecuted and possibly sentenced. Security agencies and the general public are, therefore, put on notice. An enforcement structure has been established to effect these directives to the letter."

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Maslow's Theory of Human Needs

The study adopted the Theory of Human Needs by Abraham Maslow as its theoretical framework. Human Needs theory generally proposed that all human beings have certain basic universal needs and that whenever these needs are denied, conflict is likely to occur. The theory was generally popularized by Maslow (1954), Burton Rosenberg (1984) and Maxneef (1991).

These theorists all agreed that the basic cause of most of the intractable conflict was the underlying need of people to meet their needs which can either be individual, groups and societal based. Human needs are very essential as this will help every human to live and attain some level of well-being in any ramification of life. Hence the position of the human needs theory is that the unavailability of any alternative means to meet the needs of individual or group is usually what triggers violence or conflict.

Violence also might occur when humans require understanding, respect and consideration for their needs. These needs are not only food, water and shelter, but also biological needs such as: participation, identification, understanding and recognition. There are also both physical and non-physical elements that are needed for a successful Human growth and development, as well as those things humans are likely driven to attain Sandra. Maslow had earlier identified and placed those needs in a hierarchical order. To him, each need has specific ranking or order of attainment.

1. Primary/physiological needs are; food, water and shelter. These are followed by the need for safety and security, and then followed by belonging or love, self-esteem and finally rounding up by enumerating personal fulfillment.
2. Safety/Security- The need for structure stability and freedom from fear and anxiety.
3. Belongingness/Love- The needs to be accepted by others and to have strong personal tie with one's family, friends and identify groups.

4. Esteem needs are the fourth level in Maslow's hierarchy and include self-worth, accomplishment and respect. Maslow classified esteem needs into two categories:
 - i) esteem for oneself (dignity, achievement, mastery, independence) and
 - ii) the desire for reputation or respect from others (e.g., status, prestige). Maslow indicated that the need for respect or reputation is most important for children and adolescents and precedes real self-esteem or dignity.
5. Self-actualization needs are the highest level in Maslow's hierarchy, and refer to the realization of a person's potential, self-fulfillment, seeking personal growth and peak experiences. Maslow (1943) describes this level as the desire to accomplish everything that one can, to become the most that one can be.

METHODOLOGY

This study is basically a qualitative research, because the paper adopts secondary sources of data sourced from books, journals, magazines, internet and other relevant sources of information that relate to the subject matter. The ex-post facto research design, and content analysis were adopted as method of data analysis for the study.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

From the research, it was found that Scavengers are directly responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis. The following fact from the state government has cleared every doubt that Scavengers are equally responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis. "Government has banned the activities of scavengers in the state. Secretary to State Government, Dr. Emmanuel Ekuwem, in a statement on Tuesday, said the ban is due to the acts of criminality and threat to peaceful inter-ethnic relationships posed by the scavengers in the state. He also said the government's action is also in consonance with "public sentiments amidst popular complaints against the activities of these scavengers who wantonly violate peoples' properties, stealing and assaulting law-abiding citizens in the process (The Pioneer News Paper of April 5, 2023)."

CONCLUSION

Based on the finding that that Scavengers are directly responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis and with a concrete fact from the state government which proves that Scavengers are equally responsible for security challenges in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Uyo metropolis, it can be concluded that despite the intervention of government, scavenging business is still going on in the state with rebranded strategies, like using bags, instead of wheel barrows to convey their wares and or waiting at their dump sites for citizens to bring the condemn materials to sell for the at exorbitant prices, etc.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above finding and conclusion, it is recommended that:
The State Government should strengthen its Task Force on Scavenging and other Criminal

Offenses by providing special funding and also conscripting members of the rural communities to watch over the activities of scavengers in their various communities and report any criminal element to law enforcement agency in the state.

REFERENCES:

- Binford, L. R. (1985). "Human ancestors: Changing views of their behavior". [Journal of anthropological archaeology. Elsevier](#): 4 (4). 292–327.
- Burton, J. W. (1984). Conflict: Human needs theory (vol.2). Martin's press.
- Castilla, A.M.; Richer, R.; Herrel, A.; Conkey, A.A.T.; Tribuna, J.; Al-Thani, M. (2011). First evidence of scavenging behaviour in the herbivorous lizard *Uromastix aegyptia microlepis*. *Journal of arid environments*. 75 (7): 671–673.
- Getz, W. (2011). "[Biomass transformation webs provide a unified approach to consumer resource modelling](#)". *Ecology Letters*. 14 (2): 113–124.
- Henning, J.; Wibawa, H.; Morton, J.; Usman, T.B.; Junaidi, A.; Meers, J. (2010). "[Scavenging ducks and transmission of highly pathogenic avian influenza, Java, Indonesia](#)". *Emerging infectious diseases*. 16 (8): 1244–1250.
- Lieberman, D.; Bramble, D. (2007). [The evolution of marathon running: Capabilities in humans](#). *Adis data information BV*. p. 288. Retrieved 2017-03-15 and used 2024-08-28.
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A Theory of human motivation. *Psychological review*, 50(4), 370-96
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). Motivation and personality. Harper and row.
- Max-Neef, M. A. (1991). *Human scale development conception, application and further reflections*. The apex press.
- O'Bryan, C.J.; Holden, Matthew, H.; Watson, J.E.M. (2019). "The meso-scavenger release hypothesis and implications for ecosystem and human well-being". *Ecology letters*. 22 (9): 1340–1348.
- Tan, C.K.W.; Corlett, R.T. (2011). "Scavenging of dead invertebrates along an urbanization gradient in Singapore". *Insect conservation and diversity*. 5 (2): 138–145.
- The Pioneer News Paper of April 5, 2023, pp. 1-3.
- Turner, K. L.; Abernethy, E. F.; Conner, L. M.; Rhodes, O.E.; Beasley, J. C. (2017). "[Abiotic and biotic factors modulate carrion fate and vertebrate scavenging communities](#)". *Ecology*. 98 (9): 2413–2424.
- Udoh, U.S. (2017). Rural electrification and rural development in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. *AKSU journal of management sciences (AJOMAS)*, volume 2, no. 1, pp. 85-91.
- Udoh, U.S. (2021). Public financial management and rural development in Akwa Ibom State, 2008-2017. *AKSU journal of management sciences (AJOMAS)*, volume 5, no. 1, pp. 17-44.
- Udoh, U.S. and Monday, E.U. (2021). Security challenges and national integration during Nigeria's fourth republic. *AKSU Journal of management sciences (AJOMAS)*, volume 6, no. 1&2, pp. 180-194.
- Udoh, U.S. (2024). Open defecation and public health: A case study of the riverine areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International journal of contemporary issues and trends in research (IJCITR)*, volume 2, issue 2, pp. 61-87.

- Udoh, U.S. and Fingesi, R. (2022). Environmental pollution and sustainable waste management process in Akwa Ibom State: Implications on public health and socio-economic development. *Social sciences and management international journal (SSMIJ)*, volume 3, issue 1, version 1, pp. 38-61.
- Udoh, U.S. and Obot, M.D. (2023). Banditry and socio-economic development in Nigeria: 2015-2021. *Social sciences and management international journal*, volume 4, issue 2, pp. 50-73.
- Udoh, U.S., Iyoho, U.O. and Akpabio, U.U. (2023). Fuel subsidy removal policy and its toll on the living standard of the rural people of the oil producing communities in Niger-Delta region of Nigeria: A case of Akwa Ibom State. *IJCITR international journal of contemporary issues and trends in research*, volume 1, issue 3, pp. 1-22.
- Udoh, U.S., Udobia, U.J. (2023). Power outage and its implications on value chain along Aba and Itu national grid of Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities in Akwa Ibom State. *GJCH global journal of communication and humanities*, volume 2, issue 2, pp. 101-140.
- Wille, M.; McBurney, S.; Robertson, G.J.; Wilhelm, S.I.; Blehert, D.S.; Soos, C.; Dunphy, R.; Whitney, H. (2016). ["A pelagic outbreak of avian cholera in North American Gulls Scavenging as a primary mechanism for Transmission?"](#). *Journal of wildlife diseases*. **52** (4): 793–802.